

HiPEAC 2022 Conference

Safety-Critical Collaborative Systems: Convergence to future Cyber-Physical Systems

A White Paper

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FRACTAL, VALU3S & ARROWHEAD TOOLS**

Prepared by

Alois Zoitl, University Lin, Austria

Carles Hernandez Luz, UPV, Spain

Zoltán Micskei, BME, Hungary

Charles Robinson, Thales, France

With contributions from workshop participants.

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Introduction

This report provides the feedback from the discussions of multiple communities contributing to large-scale safety-critical systems, also called cyber-physical systems (CPS). The focus is particularly for converging on interests supporting bridging of technologies between these communities and holistic strategies, a topic of interest to all stakeholders including product-line and policy managers. The paper provides a foundation and positioning following a first series of workshops supporting this new approach to bringing the CPS communities together. There was general agreement from participants that we should continue this CPS segment at the yearly HiPEAC conferences. Future white papers associated with this segment are planned to also contain recommendations to support converging strategies, gaining wider coverage of communities and also advising the European Commission. CPS involve a wide spectrum of stakeholders, some of the basic and essential ones are shown in the diagram.

We are living in an age of high individuality, which has brought many benefits to humanity, while at the same time restricting other capacities for collaboration and sustainability. We see this cumulative cultural effect clearly on nature including climate change and throw-away products, but also for shorter time-scales such as in enterprises, where yearly goals rule over longer term and higher value generation. Similarly, this individuality affects the technology domain, where silo approaches to research and evaluation dominate, already rendering interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary research [Stavridou][Prager], more challenging, but also with a longer development cycle often vying against quick wins with fewer long-term benefits. This is a context in which we find research on CPS. This research focuses on physically interactive collaborating products[Robinson1], formed by the aggregation of many contributing technologies. These include influences from the market and product-line, technical advances from functional properties, system-level functionalities, enabling technologies, and of course the aggregating tools and techniques for bridging these communities. CPS represents an important part of our future, founded on much critical national infrastructure and in many domains such as manufacturing, transport, medicine and robotics.

In recent years, there has been a focus on how to better enable the contributing communities to collaborate on creating future CPS. This is called a wicked problem by the interdisciplinary research community. "It is characterised as being complex, multi-dimensional, transversal, uncertain and with different and potentially contradictory definitions" [Raymond][Bark]. It is natural to split up a complex problem into smaller individual problems, or research topics, but the subsequent challenge is the collaboration approach that enables us to bring the solutions together to treat the original problem. To manage convergence of research for communities in the safety-critical domain, it has been

proposed that a centre of gravity is needed[Robinson2] for bridging across these communities, and that a solution is interfacing with the dependability, in particular the real-time, safe and secure aspects. Dependability is a common point of interest in which all contributing communities are invested, as improvements here accelerate the adoption of technologies, and advancement of newer safety-critical products on the market.

So our discussions in this CPS segment, at the HiPEAC conference, were structured with this in mind and supporting convergence on aggregative techniques between the communities. Each workshop is led by a key technical community, where interfacing with dependability will be a common discussion point. Participation by influencers including product line managers, policy makers and other parties from the market of safety-critical collaborative systems was encouraged.

We now advance to the feedback provided during the first series of workshops looking to broach the subject of bridging technologies between the contributing communities for safety-critical systems. The workshops ENHANCE, FORECAST and STEADINESS took place as a cyber-physical systems (CPS) segment at the HiPEAC 2022 conference. This joint initiative was led by projects supporting CPS development including 1-SWARM, SELENE, ADVANCE, Arrowhead Tools, FRACTAL, VALU3S and HiPEAC.

Discussion: Enabling Technologies and Dependability in Cyber-Physical Systems (ENHANCE)

Discussions were focused on the following main topics.

Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning

As in many other domains also for safety-critical systems (CPS) the recent advances in Artificial Intelligence (AI) in general and machine learning in specific have a tremendous impact on designing and operating them. But especially for dependable CPS (our discussions focus on the dependable aspect), AI and machine learning algorithms pose special challenges. Topics discussed during the sessions are:

- If AI acts autonomously without human intervention or even not following the human and something fails, what happens?
- Dependable CPS are typically interacting with human operators with different backgrounds. These operators need to understand the intention of AI algorithms and the consequences of operator as well as AI decisions. This falls under the research topic explainable AI[Ferri].
- As CPS often works on a limited amount of data or on data that can not be easily reproduced or even produced (e.g., failures, crashes) it is of interest if there are algorithms that are preferable for such situations. For the participants it would be of further interest if there are algorithms that require a certain type of data and how it needs to be organised and classified.
- In the same direction are questions about quantitative vs. qualitative assessment of AI algorithms, so that changes to the environment can be handled by the trained model.
- Also interesting applications of AI in our domain were presented and discussed:
 - a) Anomaly/outliers detection for improving Robots reliability
 - b) Task related metrics on health care data [Nurmi]

c) Monitoring of operational behaviour

System Specification and Testing

Correct behaviour is one of the main requirements of dependable CPS. Ensuring this is a tremendous effort. New approaches on how to address this topic are in high demand. One approach that has been discussed is Behaviour Driven Development (BDD) with using for example the Gherkin Language [Gherkin]. The goal of this approach is to start with defining the intended behaviour on component or subsystem level and verify or test this intended behaviour during the whole development process.

As our systems of systems get larger and larger we see that certain system properties are emerging in an emergent fashion. This increases testing and verification effort. Testing each individual component is rather easy and well understood. This allows providing certain guarantees of component properties and behaviour. However, predicting the resulting properties and behaviour when combining components is hard. Therefore still issues are discovered during integration testing. Reasons are among others that there exists still undocumented “common knowledge” in the heads of the engineers. What is required is a model for representing systems of systems and analysing on this model its properties.

Automatic Generation of Digital Twins

Digital Twin (DT) approaches are seen as an important and valuable approach to improve the system development. Especially with very detailed DT it is possible to use simulation for training a reinforcement model (e.g., legged robots control[Rudin]) and therefore overcome some of the limitations of insufficient data needed for AI algorithms as identified above. Another example discussed with the simulation of a kitchen for robot arm interaction.

The latter however also brought up a big drawback in DT development: all the models were developed manually. This is for many application areas too much effort and not commercially viable. Therefore a critical issue of DT is their generation. There are approaches that follow a step by step refinement using human support but with more and more automation support. Other approaches are utilising machine learning in parallel to modelling[Azangoo] for deriving the required DT models. Still one issue remains as research challenges how to cope with uncertainties and disturbances of the real world development process. Questions to be answered include:

- Combining multiple sources, but how?
- Tracking system changes
- Dealing with complexity
- Dark Data

Standards

The different domains of dependable CPS are strongly regulated and influenced by standards. These standards regulate not only how systems are built, tested and verified, but they also provide domain specific languages, modelling approaches, and data storage formats. Standards identified in the discussion are:

- SysML[SysMLv2]
- STPA, System Theoretic Process Analysis
- Aerospace
 - a) RTCA DO-178
 - b) EASA AI Roadmap [EASA]
 - c) ASTM F3269 - An Industry Standard on Run Time Assurance for Aircraft Systems | AIAA [Nagarajan]
- Production automation
 - a) IEC 61131-3 and IEC 61499
 - b) AutomationML
 - c) OPC UA for semantic rich data interface

This list is not exhaustive and focused on the background of the participants. Issues identified are the missing interoperability between domains and inside these the siloed tools and methodologies.

Tools and Tool Chains for Engineering

Developing dependable CPS is a challenging task. Many disciplines have to work together. A seamless data exchange for any engineering artefacts is a key enabler for an efficient and effective development process. This can only be achieved with tool support. A major challenge identified during the discussion is how individual tools covering certain aspects of the development process can be formed into toolchains. The goal for these toolchains is to reduce the gaps in the individual steps but also allow the tracing of requirements along the development process. Furthermore, this shall enable agile development processes with short feedback loops.

An ongoing discussion point is the nature of the modelling and developing languages as well as the tools to be used for developing CPSs:

- Is there an advantage in textual languages or are graphical languages better suited?
- What is the best tool for development?

The common agreement reached is that the tools and languages should not be at the forefront of the decision. It is better to first decide on the right formalism for solving certain problems and based on that choose the languages and tools.

In general a tendency for graphical languages for the systems engineering aspects was identified. What can be generally said is that most tools for domain specific graphical or visual modelling and programming languages are niche tools. They mostly lack the comfort and usability people are used to from other tools or apps. For tool developers this is a high investment that is hard to justify. New means of tool development are needed that reduce the tool development effort and provide high quality tools. Furthermore new approaches for assessing usability and how to translate the results to tool enhancements.

Finally a topic only partly covered in research, but crucial for industrial adoption, is how to manage artefacts across the life-cycle of systems. This includes the management of releases, maintaining libraries and version control. Especially version control for graphical models is a challenge. Some approaches address it by working with the textual representation. But this is limiting and requires a mental switch for users, which leads to a bad user experience.

Discussion: Functional Properties and Dependability in Cyber-Physical Systems (FORECAST)

CPS covers a diverse spectrum of functional properties including Computation, Sensing, Physical Actions, Energy Support and Coordinated Collaboration amongst others. The dependability of CPS relies on the ability to guarantee that such functional properties are preserved during the product lifetime.

Products from different domains need to adhere to the specific development guidelines defined in each domain specific standard (e.g ISO26262 for road vehicles). Thus, functional properties dependability strongly relies on the ability to verify at different product stages –from early design to system deployment – that such properties meet the predefined safety and security goals. As the complexity of new CPS applications grows, the verification of functional properties becomes very challenging which calls for radically new methods and tools as well as new components able to deal with this new scenario.

Dependability in the context of functional properties, and especially in computing, is usually associated with the absence of errors at the outputs of the system. However, from an overall perspective and for certain systems, the dependability of the system may also rely on the ability to provide timely responses to the requested actions. Similarly, for battery powered devices, the ability to perform tasks in the predefined energy budgets also affects the dependability of the system. In general, functional properties are at the core of the CPS dependability and thus, for each functional property –and for the system as a whole– specific protection mechanisms are required.

Workshop Discussions

The FORECAST workshop program included presentations from different aspects affecting the dependability of functional properties such as low-energy computing CPS, computing platforms for applications with strong real-time requirements, fault-tolerant systems, and cognitive computing for edge applications.

We also held an open discussion session aimed at bridging the different communities that produce CPS and centering the discussions on the dependability aspects. The open discussions between the different communities were centred around the following topics:

- We discussed what are the main aspects that affect dependability in each of the communities. Many of these aspects such as availability, absence of errors, standards compliance, diverse redundancy in all components (sensors, processing, actuators) are commonly accepted by all communities as the key aspects of a dependable CPS.
- The FORECAST (functional) community put significant emphasis on system heartbeat (real-time properties) than other communities. Computing part of the FORECAST community

is well represented in HiPEAC but other aspects such as sensing or actuators design need more representation.

- We have identified incremental certification as a key aspect in all CPS communities to enable the industry adoption of technologies produced in research projects. New standards easing the replacement of components can mitigate or help to close this gap. Unfortunately, many domain and system specific features jeopardise defining a common framework to ease components integration.
- Different domains have different levels of advancement. So priorities arrive in waves to the European Commission, e.g. plug and play technology from different sectors has various levels of maturity.
- Many technologies are developed in each community with apparent clear advantages. However, technology adoption is limited and actually the most important roadblock for the creation of new innovative CPS products.

New research directions identified

During the FORECAST workshop several topics were identified as potential new research directions:

- **AI functional dependability and explainability and its relationship with safety-critical standards.** Systems that rely on the outputs of artificial intelligence models need to clearly establish how the system will behave in known and unknown scenarios. Existing approaches limit the applicability of AI functionalities to system aspects that do not compromise the reliability and dependability of the system (i.e best-effort tasks). However, this is just a workaround and new fundamental approaches tackling the problem of AI dependability are needed to fully leverage AI capabilities in next generation autonomous systems.
- **New methodologies and techniques to verify functional properties with the goal of easing technology adoption (incremental verification).** Research prototypes do usually incorporate technologies that are far beyond what one can find in market products. In the context of safety-related applications this gap is even larger due to the need of more exhaustive verification and validation procedures. Developing radically new technologies for this domain will face innumerable troubles to reach final products. Thus, new research ideas should also make special emphasis on how they can be incorporated in existing industrial procedures.
- **Approaches to bridge computing, sensing and acting aspects of CPS.** While many different parts of a CPS contribute to defining its functional properties, those aspects are generally researched by different communities that usually lack a global view of the most important challenges in each of these domains. For instance, new approaches that integrate all aspects in a holistic manner to maximise the efficiency of the system are needed. Actually, this approach is currently being explored in edge processors that design the computer architecture according to the type of sensors they integrate.

Discussion: System Engineering and Dependability in Cyber-Physical Systems (STEADINESS)

System Engineering takes a holistic, top-down approach to design and develop complex systems such as safety-critical cyber-physical systems. System Engineering methodologies and practices **look at the system as a whole**: their aim is to collect and specify system-level requirements and guarantees such as dependability or performance. In recent years many organisations have moved from a document-centric to a **model-based approach**, where various general or domain specific modelling languages are used to capture the different viewpoints of the systems. Such modelling languages and the accompanying tools (model editors, simulators, code generators etc.) could be organised into Model-Driven Engineering (MDE) workflows that support the systems design and development lifecycle.

Software is the driving factor in many industries, but it brings many **challenges to safety-critical systems**. Therefore, experts from the MDE, embedded system, real-time systems, high-performance computing communities participated at the **STEADINESS** workshop to discuss:

1. how system engineering can help to manage the ever-increasing complexity of CPS,
2. how the gap between the current MDE languages/methods and the underlying software/hardware framework used to implement trustworthy CPS could be reconciled.

Discussions were focused on the following main topics.

System engineering's advantages and challenges

According to the experiences of many participants, one of the main goals of system engineering in the development of safety-critical systems is to **support traceability**. Verification & validation (V&V) artefacts, implementation modules or parts of the underlying platform need to be connected to system-level properties through traceability links to be able to analyse the various dependability properties and reason about the current guarantees of the system.

However, system engineering practices aggregating different models and technologies face challenges when **developing future cyber-physical systems**.

- **Increasing scale of systems**: we are rarely dealing with isolated, compact systems; instead connected systems of systems are becoming the new norm even in safety-critical systems. The scalability of tools is frequently benchmarked, but how can we scale system engineering processes or even system engineers? How can we share and document all the implicit knowledge of all the diverse stakeholders participating in the design and implementation?
- **Emerging behaviours**: partly due to the increase in scale and the interconnected nature of today's and tomorrow's systems, we are experiencing more and more emerging behaviours: systems work correctly on their own, but when they are co-located or are cooperating, behaviour not envisioned for either system could be produced. Who will be responsible for analysing such potential emerging behaviours? How can we guarantee the dependability of systems of systems?
- **Modelling too much or too little**: System engineering needs to strike a delicate balance between modelling too much or too little. On one hand, models need to be detailed enough to enable

meaningful analysis. On the other hand, system-level models should not go too deep, otherwise they start to remodel parts that are already modelled in specialised languages (e.g., mechanical, hardware, software). How to know what should be the scope of system engineering models? How to import or link data that exists already in other models?

Modelling languages for designing future CPS

Modelling languages are the cornerstone of model-driven engineering. Several modelling languages and methodologies were mentioned at the workshop (SysML, Capella, OPM), which were used by the participants. Independently of the languages, the following capabilities were raised that are important for **future modelling languages and environments**.

- **Viewpoints supporting system engineering:** system engineering is a complex process with many stakeholders, tasks, and artefacts to produce. Modelling languages suited for designing complex, safety critical CPSs should be able to present different views and viewpoints e.g., for simulation or V&V and connect/import to other environments used for the detailed modelling or simulation results. How can we easily connect models or items in different modelling languages? How can we support traceability in such interconnected models?
- **Sophisticated tooling for productivity:** even a well-designed, powerful modelling language will be useless if there are no tools to realise the full potential of the language. Programming languages and IDEs made significant progress in the last decades to ease the work of programmers. Can we have easily usable refactoring, diffing, or visualising of system modelling languages? Do we have fast static analysers and checkers for models? Push-a-button simulation or testing frameworks?
- **Standardised APIs for integration:** even heavyweight modelling environments are not used in isolation nowadays, but as part of a larger workflow or toolchain. Connecting and integrating tools could be simplified if modelling tools offer and support standardised interfaces. These interfaces or APIs can be part of the language specification or could be a language-independent technology (e.g. [OSLC]). How to convince vendors to use such interoperable interfaces?
- **Considering the execution platform:** many system engineering practices emphasise the separation of functional specification from the implementation and the execution platform. However, in many organisations and companies the physical execution platform is frequently fixed or has numerous constraints that are not realistic/economically feasible to change. The typical challenge is that the system design is usually done by teams different from those who have deep knowledge about the capabilities of the execution platform. When to take into consideration the execution platform in system engineering? How can we add tailored information to the system design understandable by other stakeholders? Can we start thinking early about how to map technology onto the platform?

An example for a modern system engineering language is the **upcoming v2 version of the System Modeling Language (SysML)**. Key features that reflect on the above focus points are the followings: 1) the language will have a textual syntax that make version control or calculating diffs much less effort, 2) an API to access the model is part of the language specification, and 3) SysMLv2 will offer native language constructs to describe analysis or verification cases and link to results in other tools.

Verification and Validation (V&V)

Several participants stressed that verification and validation is a key activity that differentiates safety-critical systems from “normal” systems. V&V must be systematic and must adhere to recommendations in safety related standards in order to obtain necessary certifications. However, such comprehensive V&V requires a large amount of effort that could take a significant part of the engineering costs. Therefore, techniques that could reduce the effort of V&V or increase the safety of the system to be developed is of uttermost importance.

- **Automatic generation of V&V artefacts:** Manually creating V&V artefacts (test cases, models for safety analysis, assurance cases etc.) requires huge effort and could be a repetitive task in many cases. Several participants agreed that completely automatic verification of industrial systems is usually not possible or not realistic. However, verification and validation activities can be supported by automatically generating some artefacts (or at least templates or skeletons) that can significantly reduce the effort needed. What artefacts are feasible to produce in different application domains? What information is needed in the system model to support such automated generation?
- **Formal verification approaches:** Faults found and corrected early in the development process could reduce engineering costs considerably. Formal verification techniques offer early verification of design models and make possible the synthesis of correct-by-design implementations. However, the scalability and applicability of such techniques is a challenge yet to be solved. In which phase of system engineering is formal verification suitable to use? What (parts of) design models can be successfully and realistically verified?
- **Incremental approaches:** In many industrial settings the product is not a new system developed from scratch, but instead the enhancement or customization of a previous system, which has already been certified. Can we incrementally produce materials for certification to not recertify the whole system? Do safety standards or external auditors allow such reuse or incrementality of certification?

The participants of the workshop came from different research communities (MDE, programming languages, dependability, real-time) or application domains (industrial automation, railway, aerospace), but the presented questions and challenges aligned with their experiences and felt relevant.

Concluding Remarks

These workshop discussions opened new doors such as revealing where technologies from one domain could solve bottlenecks in another domain. There were also insights gained from the multi-stakeholder discussions for these safety-critical systems (CPS), such as the varying maturity of technologies across domains and the likely impact this has on funding. Consensus from participants encouraged that this approach for bringing the contributing communities together was worthwhile to continue. A follow-up session is being planned for the next HiPEAC conference. The next white paper will seek to also derive recommendations for this multi-community domain and to the Commission, potentially including feedback on enhancing the workshop approach to best support the common interests.

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Appendix

Attendees (and report contributors)

(Should ask participants that they are happy with acknowledgement)

Alessandro Palumbo	Uni of Rome Tor Vergata
Christian Ewert	University of Lübeck, Germany
Fabio Federici	Collins
Francisco Bas	BSC
Guillem Cabo	BSC
Ilya Tuzov	UPV
Jan Fiedor	BUT\Honeywell
Johan Klockars	CAES Gaisler
José Flich	UPV
Konrad Swarz	Siemens
Laura Medina	UPV
Leonid Azriel	Technion
Luca Bertaccini	ETH Zurich
Luis Miguel Pinho	ISEP Porto
Manolis Marazakis	FORTH
Martin Matschnig	Siemens
Michael Rogenmoser	ETH Zurich
Midhun Xavier	LTU, Lulea
Mitchell Peterson	Reflex Aerospace
Pablo Andreu	UPV
Raúl de la Cruz	Collins
Shufan Yang	Edinburgh Napier
Sergi Alcaide	BSC

Tomas Picornell	UPV
Tommaso Cucinotta	Scuola SUP Sant'Anna, Pisa
Wolfgang Kunz	TU Kaiserslautern

Workshop Agendas

ENHANCE Agenda

10:00 to 10:20 Welcome and Introduction. Workshop topic selection

10:20 to 11:00 Paper Presentation session 1

- A heterogeneous flexible automation system development using IEC 61499
- Analysis as a Service Using OSLC and the Eclipse Arrowhead IoT Framework

11:00 to 11:30 Refreshments

11:30 to 13:00 Bar Camp (Group Workshop)

13:00 to 14:00 Lunch Break

14:00 to 15:00 Keynote by Steve Bitar from ExxonMobil Research and Engineering, USA (Abstract and Bio in the program tab)

15:00 to 15:40 Paper Presentation Session 2

- Challenges in Visual Anomaly Detection for Autonomous Mobile Robots
- Intelligent debugger for IEC 61499: explanation module

15.40 to 16:00 Refreshments

16:00 to 17:20 Paper Presentation Session 3

- Towards cloud-based virtual commissioning for IEC 61499-based automation systems
- Sitting on a gold mine: the story of the process industry's automatic formation of a digital twin
- Application Behavior Models for IEC 61499
- Plant model generation from event log using ProM for formal verification of CPS

17:20 to 17:30 Closing

FORECAST Agenda

10.00 Welcome, key note and general discussion on CPS

- Leveraging the PULP Platform to Build Reliable Systems talk by Luca Bertaccini (ETH) and Michael Rogenmoser (ETH)

11.00 Refreshments

11.30 Functional property technologies bridging to dependability.

- SafeSoftDR: A Library to Enable Software-based Diverse Redundancy for Safety-Critical Tasks by Sergi Alcaide (BSC)
- Fault-tolerant capabilities of a NOEL-V processor system by Johan Klockars (Cobham Gaisler)
- System Level Instrumentation Framework (SLIF) by Ahsan Saeed (BOSCH) (cancelled)
- Group Discussion

13.00 Lunch

14.00 Functional Properties for Intelligent Systems

- Towards Cognitive Awareness on the Edge for Industrial Applications by Martin Matschnig (SIEMENS)
- Low-power Inference in Medical Applications by Jose Flich (UPV)

14:45 Real-time properties

- End-to-end QOS for the Open Source safety-relevant RISC-V SELENE Platform by Pablo Andreu (UPV)
- Model-based FPGA design flow for real-time applications: A preliminary case study by Tommaso Cucinotta (Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna)

15:30-16:00 Wrap-up

STEADINESS Agenda - Half-day workshop

10.00 Welcome

10.10 Systems communities in CPS (Dr. C Robinson, Thales)

11.00 Refreshments

11.30 System Engineering technologies bridging to dependability. (Dr. Z. Micskei, BME)

13.00 Lunch